

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL COMPRESSION ANALYSIS OF 3D X-RAY CT SCANNED UNI-DIRECIONAL PULTRUDED CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Mechanical properties, Plastic deformation, Compressive strength, Finite element analysis (FEA), Mechanical testing

ABSTRACT

This work presents a numerical prediction of the compressive strength of pultruded carbon composite profiles. Predictions based on input data acquired through 3D X-ray computed tomography scanning. The X-ray data are derived from real uni-directional pultruded samples and used for the determination of the fiber orientation distribution of the composite through the structure tensor analysis mathematical method. The fiber and matrix material properties are determined through experimental testing both of composite samples derived from the same pultruded profiles as the ones of the X-ray scanned specimens and of matrix samples. The compressive strength of the composite is acquired and compared to the numerically obtained values. Apart from the fiber and matrix properties, the fiber orientation distribution, the voxel size and the fiber diameter serve as input for the model. The model is two-dimensional, subjected to compressive loading, while material homogenization of the fibers and matrix is performed. The formulation ensures that the model is mesh independent. Apart from the prediction of the compressive strength, the numerical model provides information on the kink band formation in the material sample. The results show the effect of each X-ray scanned slice's fiber orientation distribution to the material's strength. It is also shown that the numerical compressive strength values could serve as a prediction for the actual ones in the case that the fiber orientation distribution is the sole material variation found in a pultruded composite. This study forms the basis for a more extensive investigation presented in ongoing work.

1 INTRODUCTION

Pultruded unidirectional carbon fiber composites are commonly used as structural elements in wind turbine blades, particularly in the load carrying spar cap, where high compressive strength is required [1-4]. Due to the nature of the manufacturing process, pultrusion is related with enhanced fiber straightness and constant cross section of the manufactured composite. However, small deviations in fiber orientation can significantly reduce the material's capacity to sustain compressive loads and trigger kink band formation [5]. This study introduces a numerical modelling approach to predict the

compressive strength of such composites, using fiber orientation distribution extracted from X-ray computed tomography (CT) scans as the primary input.

Fiber orientations will lead to shear loads in the matrix material. When the matrix shear loading capacity is reached, excessive fiber rotation occurs resulting in the formation of kink bands [5]. Researchers have used extensively 3D X-ray scanning techniques to develop three-dimensional methods to estimate the fiber orientation distribution in real composite materials [6, 7]. Volumetric data of composite sample acquired by X-ray CT scanning can be used as an input for the structure tensor analysis, an image analysis mathematical method for the determination of the fiber orientation, as described by Jeppesen et al. [8, 9]. The structure tensor analysis, used in this work as well, allows for the calculation of the local gradient of intensity in a neighbourhood around each voxel of the examined scanned volume, and is stored in a matrix. Through eigenvalue decomposition of this matrix, the dominant fiber orientation can be found and, subsequently, being mapped to the integration points of a finite element (FE) model's mesh [10].

Kyriakides et al. [11] and Vogler et al. [12] developed a two-dimensional discretized model to study the mechanisms of compression of unidirectional fiber composites, including fiber orientation variations. The kink band formation was investigated while it was found that fiber non-uniformity affects greatly the compressive limit load. A two-dimensional numerical model was developed by Christoffersen and Jensen [13, 14] to study the kink band formation on composites. The material was described by an elastic-plastic constitutive law, while homogenization was applied on the constitutive properties. Ferguson et al. [7, 15] adapted the method above and, after extracting the fiber orientation distribution from X-ray CT scanned composite data by using the structure tensor analysis and mapping it to the model, was able to predict the compressive strength and the initiation of the kink band formation. The solution acquired following this approach is mesh dependent [16].

Fleck and Shu [17] presented a theoretical homogenized numerical model. In the model, the fiber microrotation was described by introducing a scalar kinematic variable θ , the fiber diameter served as length scale and the fiber bending's effect on the stiffness was included. Poullos and Niordson [17, 18] developed a similar homogenized numerical model. It also included a kinematic variable θ , but contrary to the one mentioned above this is a vector. Two independent constitutive material laws described the composite's components, with the fibers and the matrix following hyperelastic and hyperelastoplastic behavior respectively. Similar as above, the fiber diameter was used as length scale and the fiber bending effect on the stiffness was included. This FE model was used for the study of composite materials under compressive loading following the assumption of idealized fiber orientation imperfections. The kink band formation was thoroughly investigated and, after comparing the fiber-matrix homogenized micromechanical model with the corresponding fiber-matrix discrete one, the former was found accurate and in good agreement. Mageira et al. [20] first studied a real composite case with the method described above. Carbon fiber composite data acquired through X-ray CT scanning served as input for the model.

The presented work continues the method built in [20] by adding experimental testing to compare and evaluate the numerical obtained values of the compressive strength of real composite samples with the corresponding experimentally obtained ones. To the knowledge of the authors, a comparison between experimental and numerical values based on real data using the homogenized model developed by Poullos and Niordson is introduced for the first time here. The method includes the acquisition of 3D X-ray data from samples from a carbon composite pultruded profile. By using the structure tensor analysis, the fiber orientation distribution can be determined and serve, along with the material properties obtained after experimental compression testing, as an input for the FE model. The two-dimensional numerical model from [17, 18], built in the finite element library GetFEM, has been adapted to include the extracted fiber orientation data. The results show the kink band formation in the examined sample and the prediction of the compressive strength of it; the latter is compared with the corresponding experimental values. The work presented here are part of a larger framework, which is further developed in an extended study [21]. This study contributes to the improvement of the numerical prediction of the compressive strength of unidirectional composites by integrating real fiber orientation data with a mesh-independent homogenized finite element model.

2 THEORY

The two-dimensional numerical model is an implementation of the composite material homogenized formulation developed by Poullos and Niordson [18]. Key points of the formulation include the decomposition of the homogenized composite's kinematics into the ones of the fiber and the matrix. Apart from the displacement variable \mathbf{u} , an additional kinematic field variable, \mathbf{d} , is introduced. Both are two-dimensional vectors, while a plastic multiplier scalar variable ξ_m is also used. It describes a scaled version of the increment $\Delta\gamma_m$ of the accumulated plastic strain γ_m , between two consecutive time steps. Considering the above, there are five degrees of freedom in total per node ($u_1, u_2, d_1, d_2, \xi_m$). The method results in the model's mesh independence, meaning that the element size does not affect the results. A detailed description of the homogenized formulation can be found on [19], while more information on the presented implementation, including the calculation steps, is available on [21].

The fibers' behavior is described by standard isotropic hyper-elasticity defined by the Young's modulus E_f and the Poisson's ratio ν_f . The matrix's behavior is described by standard isotropic hyper-elastoplasticity, with the matrix's hyper-elasticity defined in a similar manner as above (by the Young's modulus E_m and the Poisson's ratio ν_m). The plasticity of the model's material is depicted through the Ramberg-Osgood constitutive law applied on the matrix. This material model can capture the non-linear strain hardening relationship, described by two fitting parameters, $\sigma_{0,m}$ and n_m . The Ramberg-Osgood material model is:

$$\varepsilon_{eq,m} = \frac{\sigma_{eq,m}}{E_m} + \frac{3}{7} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eq,m}}{\sigma_{0,m}} \right)^{n_m} \quad (1)$$

where $\varepsilon_{eq,m}$ is the effective von Mises strain and $\sigma_{eq,m}$ the effective von Mises stress for the matrix. Apart from the aforementioned fitting parameters and fiber and matrix properties, the model requires the fiber volume fraction V_f and the fiber diameter h_f as an input. The latter enables the model to account for the fiber's bending effect. The numerical model was built in GetFEM [22], an open-source FE library with interface for Python.

3 METHOD AND RESULTS

Figure 1: The developed methodology used in this work, described in a flow chart.

The methodology followed in this work, presented in Figure 1, started with the acquisition of the X-ray CT data of the unidirectional carbon composites, their analysis and, subsequently, the calculation of the fiber orientation distribution and its mapping on the FE model. Material characterization was carried out for the fibers, the matrix and the whole composite (it should be noted that in this work, the term fiber corresponds to what is considered filament, as it is widely used in similar articles). Along with the fiber orientation distribution, the extracted material properties served as the input for the numerical model. In this way, the predictions of the compressive strength and the kink band formation could be obtained. Mageira et al. [21] provides a more thorough description on the whole process and results.

3.1 X-ray CT data acquisition and results

Three samples were cut from a pultruded carbon profile. Their geometry was cylindrical as can be seen in Figure 2, with a diameter and length of 1 mm and 20 mm respectively. The samples were X-ray fully scanned at DanMAX beamline of the MAX IV synchrotron facility. The projection field was $1.2 \times 1.2 \times 1.2 \text{ mm}^3$ and the voxel size was equal to $0.55 \mu\text{m}$. Considering that the average size of the single carbon fiber diameter is $7 \mu\text{m}$, this voxel size ensured clear capture of the data, as it can be seen in the zoomed detail of Figure 2b. For the demonstration of the method and due to page limitations, only the results of the sample numbered six are presented in this work.

Figure 2: (a) The scanned unidirectional carbon composite samples. Each sample is fixed on a base used for mounting during 3D X-ray scanning. (b) Representative slice showing the cross section of one of the examined samples, as it is after reconstruction. The zoomed image shows the level of detail and quality of the scan. The characteristic kidney-shaped cross section of carbon fibers can be observed.

The two planes are annotated. The coloured lines represent the top view of the slices showing the longitudinal direction of the fibers, that can be seen in the bottom of the figure, for the yz-plane (c) and the xz-plane (d). These slices serve as an input for the structure tensor analysis.

Figure 2b show a slice of the scanned sample after reconstruction, showing the cross section of it. The images representing the slices were cropped and stacked accordingly to create a digital subvolume of the total scanned samples' volume. The subvolume had a thickness corresponding to 100 slices. Through its creation, the slices related to the planes that show the longitudinal direction of the fibers could be acquired. These slices and their corresponding subvolumes were essential for using the three-dimensional structure tensor analysis for the determination of the fiber orientation distribution. In Figure 2, the two planes, xz- and yz-, are annotated. Five slices were considered in this work, per orientation. An example of each plane's slice showing the longitudinal direction of the fibers can be seen at the bottom of the figure; these two slices and their corresponding results are the ones thoroughly presented in this work.

3.2 Material results

The material properties that serve as an input for the numerical model and thus need to be determined experimentally are the Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios of the fiber and the matrix, the fiber volume fraction and average diameter and the fitting parameters of the Ramberg-Osgood model for the matrix system. The first step was the determination of the mechanical properties of the composite material. To achieve this, samples were cut from the same pultruded profile from which the scanned samples were acquired. These samples were subjected to compressive testing. The Universal Testing Machine used had a load cell of 250 kN, and the applied testing speed was 1 mm/min. The strain range considered for the calculation of the composite's Young's modulus was 0.05 - 0.25 %, according to ISO-14126 [23]. As it can be seen in Figure 3, most of the samples broke outside their gauge area, due to the shear control of the failure [7]. For that reason, the acquired values of the compressive strength should be considered conservative.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: (a) The examined dogbone-shaped samples, after the compression test. (b) The failure outside the gauge area of most of them can be noted. For the development of the kink band outside the gauge area, please refer to [7].

The matrix was vinyl ester, with its stress-strain curve shown in Figure 4, and the values of its Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio in Table 1. As mentioned in the Theory section, the Ramberg-Osgood material model was used to describe the behavior of the matrix numerically. The values of the parameters are $\sigma_{o, m} = 104.37$ MPa and $n_m = 2.35$, and were found by fitting the Ramberg-Osgood material model on the matrix stress strain curve, as shown in Figure 4. The Young's modulus of the fibers was determined through back calculation by using the rule of mixture, since the matrix and composite material properties were already known. The detailed description and analysis of the material data are presented on [24].

Figure 4: The stress-strain curves for the fibers and the matrix (left). A zoomed area of the graph is included (right). The fit of the Ramberg-Osgood material model for the matrix can be observed, as well the numerical model's material input for the fibers.

The average values of the calculated properties are presented on the following table:

Magnitude		Composite	Matrix	Fiber
Young's modulus E	[GPa]	137.5 ± 1.7	3.55	204.8 ± 4.1
Poisson's ratio ν	[-]	–	0.4	0.26
Volume fraction	[%]	–	33.6 ± 0.9	66.2 ± 0.8
Fiber's diameter	[μm]	–	–	7

Table 1: The mechanical properties and material parameters acquired after characterization of the composite, the fiber and the matrix.

3.3 Fiber orientation distribution results

The structure tensor analysis was used to determine the fiber orientation distribution. A short description of the method is included in the introduction, along with references regarding where to find details on it. For information on how it was applied on this dataset, please refer to [21].

After the decomposition of the eigenvalues, the corresponding eigenvectors were calculated, and the dominant fiber orientation was found. For the two-dimensional model used, the representation of the fiber orientation is a two-dimensional projection of the eigenvector r_1 to the yz - or xz -plane, respectively. The subscript 1 identifies the dominant fiber orientation. To show the fiber orientation, the elevation angle φ was used, formed and calculated as shown in Figure 5. In the same figure, the elevation angle distribution on a slice is presented.

Figure 5: (a) The coordinates system used for this work, along with the dominant eigenvector r_1 , its projections at the yz- and xz-planes and the corresponding elevation angle for each case. Right next to it, the equations for the calculation of the elevation angle, per plane. (b) A yz-plane slice used for the 3D structure tensor analysis, with the elevation angle for a fiber shown. (d) The distribution of the elevation angle of the same slice as in figure 5b. (c) Distribution of the elevation angles for one slice per plane. The slices used are same as in Figure 2.

Figure 5 shows also the histogram of the distribution of the elevation angle's values for each examined plane. In the same figure, the values of the mean elevation angle φ , as well as of the mean absolute elevation angle, $|\varphi|$, are presented. The mean absolute elevation angle is chosen as a single value to represent both the magnitude and the scatter of the fiber orientation distribution [7, 24, 25]. For both planes, the vast majority of the values of the elevation angle ranged between -3° and 3° , something that is due to the unidirectionality of the pultruded material and the high quality of this manufacturing process. For the xz-plane, the mean elevation angle $\varphi = -0.50^\circ$ and the mean absolute elevation angle $|\varphi| = 1.17^\circ$. For the yz-plane, the corresponding value of the mean $\varphi = -0.07^\circ$, and for the mean $|\varphi| = 0.61^\circ$.

3.4 Mapping of the fiber orientation distribution

The fiber orientation distribution serves as an input for the numerical model by its mapping to the integration points of the elements. A file containing the distribution of the elevation angle φ regarding the undeformed slice modelled is read by the FE code. The cosine and sine of each value of the elevation angle are calculated and saved as the following unit vectors, N and T :

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos(\varphi_0) \\ \sin(\varphi_0) \end{Bmatrix} \text{ and } \mathbf{N} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\sin(\varphi_0) \\ \cos(\varphi_0) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Each pair of N and T is mapped on an integration point. The unit vector T describes the direction parallel to the fibers, while the unit vector N the direction perpendicular to the fibers. The number of the mesh elements corresponds to the size of the examined slice, through the coupling of an elevation angle value with an integration point.

3.5 Numerical results

The numerical model was built in GetFEM. The coordinate system of the simulation is similar to the one related to the X-ray CT scanned samples presented on Figure 2. The model was two dimensional and was subjected to compression.

Figure 6: The stress-strain curve, for a single numerical case (xz-plane). Three points of interest are annotated as (A): just after the start of the compressive loading, (B): at maximum compressive stress and (C): at the latest stages of the simulation. For the same points, the distribution of the matrix's Cauchy shear stresses on the examined slice is shown, with the related scale bar included on the right of the graph.

Figure 6 shows the predicted stress-strain curve of one simulated slice. In addition, the distribution of the matrix's Cauchy shear stresses at the early loading stages, at the point of failure and after it can be observed, along with the gradual formation of the kink band. The stress-strain curve follows an almost linear trend, until the maximum stress value is reached and thus failure occurs. During the compressive failure of a composite, particularly when it is unidirectional, the material's limit load is reached in an area of localized strain [27], leading to the abrupt and excessive bending of the fibers, and subsequently to the kink band formation.

In the numerical model, the stress-strain curve follows a snap-back trend, which is a characteristic of the unidirectional composite's kink band formation during a FE simulation [25]. The snap back behavior is due to the localized fiber rotation leading in a load drop which results in elastic unloading in the material outside the kink-band region.

Figure 7: The stress-strain curves of the numerical data, for both planes examined, along with the results acquired through experimental testing. The maximum stress value is marked, for each case. A fitted curve for both the numerical and the experimental response, along with the mean failure point of each case, are included.

In Figure 7, the stress-strain curves for both the experimental and the numerical (for both planes) results is shown. The initial part of the experimental and numerical curves follows a similar trend. After this, however, the trend of the experimental measurements follows a curvature, govern by the non-linearity of the fiber material [28]. The numerical results show a stiffer response, which, as argued by Ferguson et al. in [7], is expected for a two-dimensional plane strain numerical model [25].

In the same figure, the value of the mean maximum stress (annotated as mean failure point) is included. For the numerical simulations, this value is 1546 MPa (xz-plane) and 1997 MPa (yz-plane). The corresponding experimental value is 1349 MPa. These results, along with the Young’s moduli, average strain, mean elevation angle and mean absolute elevation angle are presented on Table 2. The compressive strength on yz-plane was on average 29% larger than the one of the xz-plane, and the compressive strength of xz-plane was 15% larger than the experimental values, on average. The Young’s moduli of the numerical simulations were close to the experimental value, being 6% different for the yz-plane and 8% for the xz-plane.

Magnitude		Numerical, yz-plane	Numerical, xz-plane	Experimental
Young’s modulus E	[GPa]	145.5 ± 0.2	148.0 ± 0.2	137.5 ± 1.0
Strength σ_{max}	[MPa]	1997 ± 110	1546 ± 29	1349 ± 23
Strain ε at max load	[%]	1.35 ± 0.07	1.11 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.02
Mean angle φ	[°]	0.19 ± 0.10	-0.63 ± 0.15	–
Mean absolute angle $ \varphi $	[°]	0.63 ± 0.05	1.24 ± 0.07	–

Table 2: Average values of strength, strain, mean elevation angle and mean absolute elevation angle regarding the numerical results, along with the average values for stress and strain obtained through experimental testing.

The difference between the experimental and numerical compressive strengths can be attributed to

several factors. Geometry and loading conditions of the tested samples may have introduced local stress concentrations [7], with some samples failing outside the gauge area due to shear, which the model does not capture. In addition, the volume fraction of the fibers and the matrix were considered constant in the model, while, according to Kyriakides et al. [11] and Jensen [29], the varying volume fraction leads to a decrease in the sample's ability to resist kink band formation, and thus probably to a slightly reduced compressive strength. The fiber-matrix interface, which affects load transfer, and thus the compressive strength, is also not included. Finally, as a two-dimensional model, it cannot capture out-of-plane variations in fiber orientation distribution, possibly leading to a higher numerical value of compressive strength.

Considering the above, the compressive strength predicted by the numerical model can represent the potential strength of the composite, accounting for its fiber orientation distribution, under pure compression where shear effects are negligible.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, X-ray CT images of pultruded carbon fiber reinforced composite samples were used to predict the compressive strength of the material by using a built numerical model. Key part of the two-dimensional, mesh independent, homogenized model was the inclusion of the composite's real fiber orientation distribution. The numerical results of the predicted compressive strength were compared with the corresponding experimental values, with the former being higher than the latter ones. This difference was expected, mostly due to the model being two-dimensional, the effect of shear during the experimental testing and any potential imperfections of the tested samples. Thus, the numerical results could serve as the prediction of the compressive strength of a composite considering its fiber orientation distribution. Through this work, the effect of fiber orientation distribution, dependent on pultrusion parameters, on the composite's compressive strength is shown. Based on these findings, adjustments to the pultrusion process could be made to improve the mechanical properties of wind turbine composite blades.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was funded by EU Horizon MSCA 2021 DN Reliance: REaL-tIme characterization of ANisotropic Carbon-based tEchnological fibers, films and composites, grant no. 101073040.

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I, Lars Pilgaard Mikkelsen, hereby confirm that Pinelopi Mageira, who applied for the ICCM Tsai Award, was, at the date of the abstract submission November 15th, 2024, a PhD student under my supervision at Technical University of Denmark.

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Authors Contributions

Manuscript title: EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL COMPRESSION ANALYSIS OF 3D X-RAY CT SCANNED UNI-DIRECIONAL PULTRUDED CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

Please describe the contributions of each author, referring to the taxonomy below.

Author 1 (Tsai Award Applicant): Pinelopi Mageira

- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Formal Analysis**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Investigation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Methodology**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Software**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Validation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Visualization**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

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- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**
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- Formal Analysis**
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- Investigation**
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- Methodology**
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- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
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- Other contribution**
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- Data curation**
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- Formal Analysis**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Investigation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Methodology**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Software**
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- Validation**
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- Visualization**
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- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

Author 4: Vedrana Andersen Dahl

- Conception**
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- Data curation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Formal Analysis**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Investigation**
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- Visualization**
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- Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
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Author 5: Lars Pilgaard Mikkelsen

- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**

- Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Formal Analysis**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
 - Investigation**
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 - Software**
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 - Validation**
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 - Visualization**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
 - Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
 - Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
 - Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

Conceptualization

Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims.

Data Curation

Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse.

Formal Analysis

Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data.

Investigation

Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection.

Methodology

Development or design of methodology; creation of models.

Software

Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components.

Validation

Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.

Visualization

Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation.

Writing – Original Draft Preparation

Creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).

Writing – Review & Editing

Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.